

Supporting Information for: Engineering Floquet Moiré Patterns for Scalable Photocurrents

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In this Supporting Information we first provide a semiclassical description for laser fields, then a brief description of the unit cell employed to build the commensuration supercell and support a discussion on the effect of a single tilted laser on the electronic structure of the irradiated system. We then derive the Floquet-Bloch Hamiltonian which is used throughout the manuscript, together with a definition of the time-averaged local density of states (LDOS). Additional data is given to elucidate the role of the eccentricity and polarization of the laser at the vicinity of an interface. We also give further details on the transport calculations and show LDOS calculations for the laser configuration (2) of the main text. Within the Supporting Information references are numbered as, e.g., equation S1 and Figure S1, whereas regular numbers, e.g., equation 1 and Figure 1, refer to the main article.

S1. DETAILED SEMICLASSICAL DESCRIPTION FOR LASER FIELDS

The effect of the laser on the electronic properties of the system will be described through a semiclassical approximation, as the considered average number of photons is sufficiently large. The electric field \mathbf{E} enters as a time-periodic term in the Hamiltonian, with period $\tau = 2\pi/\omega$. This will be included through the gauge $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, t) = -\partial_t \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, t)$, where \mathbf{A} is the vector potential. We begin analyzing the effect of tilting the laser incidence with respect to a 2D graphene layer, placed along the xy plane. The situation is schematically shown in Fig. 1 of the main text, where we consider two laser beams, whose incidence direction is not perpendicular to the layer, but inclined at an angle $\pm\theta$ to the z axis and along the yz plane. To proceed, we first consider a single laser with perpendicular incidence along the z axis, such that the vector potential reads:

$$\mathbf{A}_\perp(\mathbf{r}, t) = \text{Re}[\mathbf{A}_0 e^{i(\boldsymbol{\kappa} \cdot \mathbf{r} - \omega t)}], \quad (\text{S1})$$

where $\mathbf{A}_0 = A_0(\hat{e}_x + e^{i\phi}\hat{e}_y)/\sqrt{2}$, with A_0 the laser intensity and ϕ the polarization, being $\phi = 0$ ($\pi/2$) for linear (circular) polarization, respectively. The wave vector of the beam is $\boldsymbol{\kappa} = -\kappa\hat{e}_z$, and its magnitude is $\kappa = 2\pi/\lambda = \omega/c$, with c the speed of light. The vector potential for the tilted laser is obtained from a rotation in an angle θ around the x axis, yielding:

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{A_0}{\sqrt{2}} [\cos(\alpha - \omega t)\hat{e}_x + \cos(\alpha - \omega t + \phi)\cos\theta\hat{e}_y], \quad (\text{S2})$$

where $\alpha = \alpha(y) = \kappa y \sin\theta$ accounts for the spatial variation along the lattice. Therefore, the introduction of a tilted incidence of the laser generates a spatial dependence of the vector potential, yielding a supercell structure that is drawn by the commensuration wavelength of the electric field.

S2. UNIT CELL

Here we present the unit cell (shaded area in Fig. S1), composed by four carbon atoms, employed to build up the supercell of the irradiated region. The quasi-1D system is represented with an armchair nanoribbon, and the lattice vectors can be written as $\mathbf{a}_1 = 3a\hat{e}_x$ and $\mathbf{a}_2 = \sqrt{3}a\hat{e}_y$, where $a = 1.42 \text{ \AA}$ is the carbon-carbon distance. Note that the final system preserves translational invariance along the x direction, while it is composed by $\lambda/(\sqrt{3}a \sin\theta)$ unit cell repetitions in the y direction, where λ is the laser wavelength and θ the tilt angle.

Figure S1. Unit cell as an elementary block: Schematic representation of the unit cell employed to build the irradiated region. a stands for the carbon-carbon distance, \mathbf{a}_1 and \mathbf{a}_2 are the unit cell lattice vectors. Intracell hoppings are represented by black lines linking neighbor carbon atoms, while intercell hoppings are represented by blue lines.

S3. SINGLE LASER IRRADIATION WITH A TILT

Here we show that, although Eq. (S2) includes a spatial dependence in the vector potential, this does not strongly modifies the electronic structure of the system, as compared with

the case of perpendicular irradiation with an elliptically polarized laser. This is because in this case the vector potential can compactly be written as:

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{A_0}{\sqrt{2}} \text{Re} \left[e^{i(\alpha - \omega t)} (\hat{e}_x + i \cos \theta \hat{e}_y) \right], \quad (\text{S3})$$

so the spatial dependence of the field only enters as a phase, with a single polarization handedness. This is evidenced in Fig. S2, where we compare this case with the one of perpendicular irradiation with an elliptically polarized field, which would be equivalent to take Eq. (S3) with $\alpha = 0$ along the whole supercell.

In this figure, panel (a) shows the pattern drawn by the resultant vector potential for perpendicular irradiation and elliptical polarization while panel (b) corresponds to an incidence angle of $\pi/3$ and polarization $\phi = \pi/2$. Black and blue dots in these figures denote the vector field at times $t = 0$ and $\tau/8$, respectively, so the tilt of the laser manifests as the inclusion of a space-dependent phase along the y -direction. In the perturbative regime we consider here ($\zeta \ll 1$), this phase shift only incorporates subtle modifications of the LDOS, since we cannot distinguish them at least when evaluated at the physical edges of the sample (see panels c and d). However, the spatially dependent phase dynamically breaks the inversion symmetry of the system, since in general $\alpha - \omega t$ is not symmetric with respect to the center of the supercell at $y = 0$. Interestingly, this time-dependent effect, which is not visible in the LDOS, generates an imbalance in the transmission amplitudes and, with it, a zero-bias photocurrent, as shown in panel (f). Nevertheless, regarding the discussion of photocurrents in the main text, the magnitude of this current is much smaller (and not scalable) than that obtained with two tilted lasers.

It is instructive to distinguish this single laser case with the one discussed around Eq. (3) for two lasers, which can be written as:

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \sqrt{2} A_0 \text{Re} \left[e^{-i\omega t} (\cos \alpha \hat{e}_x + i \sin \alpha \cos \theta \hat{e}_y) \right]. \quad (\text{S4})$$

Here, we recognize a time-dependent phase (ωt) times a spatially dependent vector which can invert its polarization handedness. This spatial modulation of the polarization is responsible for the interface states and scalable photocurrents discussed in the main text.

S4. FLOQUET THEORY

To begin with the description of the electronic system interacting with the electric field, we consider the following nearest neighbor tight-binding Hamiltonian for a honeycomb lattice:

$$\hat{H}(t) = \sum_i \epsilon_i \hat{c}_i^\dagger \hat{c}_i - \sum_{\langle i, j \rangle} \gamma_{ij}(t) \hat{c}_i^\dagger \hat{c}_j, \quad (\text{S5})$$

where \hat{c}_i annihilates an electron at site i of the lattice, with onsite energy ϵ_i .¹ The second sum on the right-hand side runs over nearest neighbors, connected by the hopping term $\gamma_{ij}(t)$.

This term contains the time-dependent electric field, which is included through Peierls' substitution as:

$$\gamma_{ij}(t) = \gamma_0 \exp \left[i \frac{2\pi}{\Phi_0} \int_{\mathbf{r}_j}^{\mathbf{r}_i} \mathbf{dr} \cdot \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, t) \right], \quad (\text{S6})$$

with Φ_0 the magnetic flux quantum and $\gamma_0 = 2.7$ eV the bare hopping amplitude in absence of the electric field. The line integral is taken over the straight path connecting sites j and i , with positions \mathbf{r}_j and \mathbf{r}_i , respectively, and for the case $\lambda \gg a$ considered here we can approximate the field being constant along the bond. Through this way, it is possible to characterize the intensity of the lasers through $\zeta_\ell = 2\pi A_{0\ell} a / \sqrt{2} \Phi_0$.

The time-dependent hopping terms in Eq. (S6) can be conveniently written through the Jacobi-Anger expansion as

$$\gamma_{ij}(t) = \gamma_0 \sum_{m,n} i^m \mathcal{J}_m(q_{ij}^{(c)}) \mathcal{J}_n(q_{ij}^{(s)}) e^{i(m+n)\omega t}, \quad (\text{S7})$$

where \mathcal{J}_m is the m -th Bessel function of first kind and the arguments are given by:

$$q_{ij}^{(s)} = \sum_\ell \frac{\zeta_\ell}{a} [\Delta_{ij}^x \sin \alpha_{ij}^\ell + \Delta_{ij}^y \sin(\alpha_{ij}^\ell + \phi_\ell) \cos \theta_\ell],$$

$$q_{ij}^{(c)} = \sum_\ell \frac{\zeta_\ell}{a} [\Delta_{ij}^x \cos \alpha_{ij}^\ell + \Delta_{ij}^y \cos(\alpha_{ij}^\ell + \phi_\ell) \cos \theta_\ell],$$

with $\alpha_{ij}^\ell = \kappa \bar{y}_{ij} \sin \theta_\ell$ and $\bar{y}_{ij} = (y_i + y_j)/2$, the y -component of the center of the bond connecting atoms i and j . Here $\zeta_\ell = 2\pi A_{0\ell} a / \sqrt{2} \Phi_0$ sets the intensity of the lasers. Importantly, since we take nearest neighbor coupling terms, the differences $\Delta_{ij}^x = x_i - x_j$ and $\Delta_{ij}^y = y_i - y_j$ are fixed, and the y -dependence only enters through α , such that the condition $L = \lambda / \sin \theta$ still holds in this case with two laser beams whose direction of propagation is defined on the same plane and with opposite angles with respect to the z axis.

With the explicit time-dependence in the hopping terms of Eq. (S7) we are in position to derive the Floquet Hamiltonian that allows us to move the time-periodic problem into a time-independent one. According to Floquet theorem,²⁻⁴ for time-periodic Hamiltonians it is possible to find a full set of solutions to the time-dependent Schrödinger equation (TDSE). Similar to Bloch's theorem for spatially periodic systems, these can be written as $|\psi(t)\rangle = e^{-i\epsilon t/\hbar} |\varphi(t)\rangle$, where the Floquet state $|\varphi(t)\rangle$ contains the same periodicity of the Hamiltonian, i.e., $|\varphi(t + \tau)\rangle = |\varphi(t)\rangle$, with $\tau = 2\pi/\omega$, and ϵ is a time conjugate variable known as the *quasienergy*, and it is restricted to the Floquet zone $-\hbar\omega/2 \leq \epsilon \leq \hbar\omega/2$. Replacing this solution in the TDSE yields

$$\hat{H}_F |\varphi(t)\rangle = \epsilon |\varphi(t)\rangle, \quad (\text{S8})$$

where $\hat{H}_F = \hat{H}(t) - i\hbar\partial_t$ is the so-called Floquet Hamiltonian. Importantly, \hat{H}_F can be reduced to a time-independent matrix when taking a product basis in the Floquet-Sambe space $\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{R} \otimes \mathcal{T}$. Here \mathcal{R} represents the original Hilbert space and \mathcal{T} is the space of time-periodic functions. The latter can be spanned by the set of orthonormal vectors $\langle t|n\rangle = e^{in\omega t}$, with

Figure S2. (a,b) Vector potential profiles along the y direction traced in a cycle τ for perpendicular (a) and tilted (b) irradiation, respectively. The black and blue dots show the vector field values for $t = 0$ and $\tau/8$. (c,d) LDOS, on the logarithmic scale $\log[1 + \rho(-L/2) + \rho(L/2)]$, obtained at the edges of the ribbon, highlighted with arrows in (a) and (b). (e,f) Zero-bias photocurrents for configurations (a) and (b), respectively. For the configuration shown in (b), the tilt angle is $\theta = \pi/3$ and we considered circular polarization ($\phi = \pi/2$). In addition, we used $\zeta = 0.2$ and $\hbar\omega = 1.5\gamma_0$. For configuration (a) we used the same parameters of (b), but taking $\alpha = 0$ throughout the ribbon.

n an integer number. Working within the real space representation, a suitable basis for \mathcal{F} is given by the product states $|i, n\rangle = |i\rangle \otimes |n\rangle$, accounting for the lattice site i and the n th Fourier component, together with the inner product rule

$$\langle i, n | j, m \rangle = \int_0^\tau \frac{dt}{\tau} \langle i | j \rangle e^{i(m-n)\omega t} = \delta_{i,j} \delta_{n,m}. \quad (\text{S9})$$

Due to its periodicity, the Floquet states $|\varphi(t)\rangle$ can be decomposed as the following Fourier series

$$|\varphi(t)\rangle = \sum_n e^{in\omega t} |\varphi_n\rangle \quad (\text{S10})$$

and its representation in Floquet space is

$$|\varphi\rangle = \sum_{i,n} \varphi_{i,n} |i, n\rangle, \quad (\text{S11})$$

where $\varphi_{i,n} = \langle i, n | \varphi \rangle$ is the amplitude of the Floquet state at site i and Fourier harmonic n (from now on, the replica n). Within this representation, we obtain time-independent matrix elements of the Floquet Hamiltonian, $[H_F]_{i,j}^{n,m} = \langle i, n | \hat{H}_F | j, m \rangle$, but with an infinite number of replicas,

$$[H_F]_{i,j}^{n,m} = \int_0^\tau \frac{dt}{\tau} \gamma_{ij}(t) e^{i(n-m)\omega t} + n\hbar\omega \delta_{n,m} \delta_{i,j}, \quad (\text{S12})$$

In our case, the time-dependence comes from the hopping amplitudes given in Eq. (S7), such that their Fourier transform writes:

$$\gamma_{ij}^{(n)} = \gamma_0 \sum_m i^m \mathcal{J}_m(q_{ij}^{(c)}) \mathcal{J}_{n-m}(q_{ij}^{(s)}), \quad (\text{S13})$$

and it represents the transition amplitude from site j to site i with the absorption ($n > 0$) or emission ($n < 0$) of $|n|$ photons.

Given the above discussion on the spatial dependence of the vector potential, we can exploit its translational invariance along the x direction. In this sense, the supercell consists of a linear array of N unit cells along the y direction, as shown in Fig. 1. Once this structure is established, we compute the Floquet-Bloch Hamiltonian through:

$$\mathbf{H}_k = \sum_s \mathbf{H}_s e^{isk(3a)}, \quad (\text{S14})$$

where k is the electron's wave vector, restricted to the FBZ $k \in [-\pi/3a, \pi/3a)$, and the sum runs over $s = \{-1, 0, 1\}$. Here \mathbf{H}_0 is the Hamiltonian matrix for the supercell, and $\mathbf{H}_{\pm 1}$ are the coupling matrices to the neighbor supercells. These block matrices already include the photon replicas. Importantly, since we will work in the regime $\zeta \ll 1$, it is possible to safely truncate the full Floquet space by taking an adequate number of replicas, such that the observed spectrum converges.

Of particular relevance for this work is the time-averaged local density of states (LDOS), which accounts for the weight of the k state at quasienergy ϵ on the site i along the y direction. This quantity can be obtained from:

$$\rho_{i,k}(\epsilon) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \lim_{\eta \rightarrow 0^+} \text{Im} \left\{ [\mathbf{G}_k(\epsilon + i\eta)]_{i,i}^{0,0} \right\}, \quad (\text{S15})$$

where \mathbf{G}_k is the Floquet-Green matrix associated with the Floquet Hamiltonian of Eq. (S14), i.e.,

$$\mathbf{G}_k(\epsilon) = (\epsilon \mathbf{I} - \mathbf{H}_k)^{-1}. \quad (\text{S16})$$

Such calculation of the LDOS through the Green's function allows a fast and efficient reduction of the system's dimension (i.e., the number of unit cells), through what is known as the "decimation" method.⁵ Following this procedure, it is possible to evaluate the LDOS in different regions of the supercell,

even in a bulk situation with an infinite number of supercells on either side of the evaluation region.

S5. ECCENTRICITY AND POLARIZATION INCIDENCE IN BAND GAP SIZE AND FIS DISPERSION

In this section, we show the effect of the local properties of the resulting vector potential at the polarization interfaces on the band gaps and the k -dispersion of the FIS. Here it is shown that the size of the band gap is linked to the eccentricity change rate at the interfaces, while the dispersion of the FIS inside the gap is related to the direction of polarization of the linear field. To visualize this, we consider perpendicular illumination of the sample by circularly polarized light, which is modulated in one of its components by an odd function of the y coordinate, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, t) = A_0 [\cos \omega t \mathbf{e}_x + g(y) \sin \omega t \mathbf{e}_y], \quad (\text{S17})$$

or

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, t) = A_0 [g(y) \cos \omega t \mathbf{e}_x + \sin \omega t \mathbf{e}_y], \quad (\text{S18})$$

with $g(y) = -\tanh(y/\xi)$ the modulation, such that for $y = 0$ there is a change in the polarization handedness and $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is linearly polarized in either the x or y direction. Here ξ characterizes the width of the interface region and, in turn, the rate of change of the laser eccentricity.

Figure S3 analyzes the effect of the rate of change of the eccentricity, and the direction of polarization of the field at the interfaces, on the LDOS. Each panel (c-f) shows a LDOS that corresponds to a single condition of laser polarization at the interface [panel (a)] and a rate of change of the eccentricity [panel (b)]. For example, panels (c,d) and (e,f) show that, at a constant laser polarization at the interface [x for (c,d) and y for (e,f)], a higher rate of change of the eccentricity at the interface increases the band gap size. Importantly, this finds an upper bound for an ‘‘abrupt’’ interface ($\xi \rightarrow 0$), as is the case in Fig. 2(f). On the other hand, taking a given value of the eccentricity, it can be readily seen by comparing (c,e) or (d,f) that the polarization at the interface modifies the FIS dispersion. Taking into account that the interface direction coincides with the direction of the translational invariance, it can be seen that, when the linear polarization is parallel to the interface (c,d), the k -dispersion (or group velocity) of the FIS is larger, as the FIS only cover a reduced k -region of the band gap. In the second case, where the linear polarization is perpendicular to the interface (e,f), the k -dispersion of the FIS is smaller, since the FIS states go through the whole k -region spanned by the band gap. Similar results were found in Ref. [6] for interface states at the surface of a 3D topological insulator irradiated with lasers of opposite handedness.

S6. TRANSPORT SIMULATIONS

As described in the main text, the zero-bias photocurrent (also known as time-averaged pumped current) can be expressed in terms of the 0-th component of the transmission

coefficients as $\bar{\mathcal{I}} = 2e/h \int \delta\mathcal{T}^{(0)}(\epsilon) f(\epsilon) d\epsilon$, with $f(\epsilon)$ the Fermi-Dirac distribution function. These coefficients follow the Fisher-Lee formula:

$$\mathcal{T}_{\alpha\beta}^{(n)} = 4 \sum_m \text{tr}[\Gamma_\alpha^{(m)} \mathbf{G}_{\alpha\beta} \Gamma_\beta^{(n)} \mathbf{G}_{\beta\alpha}^\dagger], \quad (\text{S19})$$

where $\alpha, \beta = \{\text{L}, \text{R}\}$, $\mathbf{G}_{\alpha\beta}$ is the retarded Floquet-Green’s function, and $\Gamma_\alpha^{(n)}$ sets the escape rate at the n -th replica of the α -lead. For our purposes, the energy integral represents a rather elaborate task since the Floquet formalism implies an infinite number of replicas below the Fermi energy. However, a finite difference between the zeroth Fourier components of the transmission coefficients is only expected around the regions $\epsilon = 0$ and $\epsilon = \pm\hbar\omega/2$, where the $n = 0$ replica mix to other replicas. The energy integral could then be taken in the vicinity of these regions, supported by the assumption that the strength of the vector potential can be taken as a small parameter, so the coupling to higher-order replicas decays sufficiently fast. Therefore, in all results of the main text we restrict our analysis to replicas $n = \{-1, 0, 1\}$, whose mixture contributes to a transmission imbalance around the ZC and ZB.

S7. SUPERCELL LDOS FROM TILTED IRRADIATION WITHOUT INTERFACES

In Fig. S4 we analyze the features of the irradiation configuration (2) employed in Fig. 4(b-2). The trajectory and the eccentricity of the resulting vector potential are depicted in panel (a), which is obtained from two circularly polarized laser beams tilted at opposite angles, yielding:

$$\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \sqrt{2}A_0 \cos\left(\frac{2\pi y}{L}\right) (\cos \omega t \mathbf{e}_x + \sin \omega t \cos \theta \mathbf{e}_y). \quad (\text{S20})$$

As shown in Fig. 4(b), in this configuration no polarization interfaces are produced, and the eccentricity of the vector potential remains constant along the supercell. Note that although the vector potential vanishes at $nL/4$ with $n = \pm 1$, its handedness is conserved. Therefore, there are no changes in the Chern number in these regions. The LDOS obtained at the discrete positions depicted with arrows in panel (a), which are the same as the ones employed in Fig. 3(a) for configuration (1), are shown in Fig. S4(b-d). At positions (b) and (d) the vector potential is elliptically polarized and a corresponding band gap opening is observed in their respective LDOS. In (c) the vector potential vanishes and the laser polarization is conserved. Consequently, there is no band gap opening, and a non-topologically protected flat state is observed.

S8. FLOQUET REPLICAS, DISORDER AND PHOTOCURRENTS

In this section we discuss in more detail the connection between the occurrence of zero-bias photocurrents with spectral and transport imbalance between different Floquet replicas. In

Figure S3. Local density of states, on the logarithmic scale $\log(1 + \rho)$, evaluated at the interface of handedness inversion. (a) Vector potential profiles for x (top) and y (bottom) linear polarizations in the interface region. Red and blue lines denote right and left polarization handedness, respectively. (b) Laser eccentricity ε along the supercell for $\xi = 0.1 L$ (left) and $\xi = 0.05 L$ (right), respectively. For linear polarization $\varepsilon = 1$ and for circular polarization $\varepsilon = 0$. Note that ε is independent of the direction of the linear polarization at the interface. (c-f) LDOS around the ZB for the vector potential profiles in (a) and eccentricities in (b). The shaded blue areas denote the associated energy gap at the interface. The used parameters are $\hbar\omega = 1.5 \gamma_0$, $\zeta = 0.1$ and $L = 800 l_0$, with $l_0 = \sqrt{3}a$ the length of the unit cell.

Figure S4. Vector potential (top panel) and polarization eccentricity (bottom panel) profiles along the y direction of the supercell for a cycle τ of the tilted irradiation described in Eq. (S20). The colors denote left (blue) and right (red) polarizations, respectively. The black dots in the top panel show the vector field values for $t = 0$. (b-d) LDOS obtained at discrete positions for the bulk of the irradiated region at positions highlighted with arrows in (a). Lasers parameters are : $\theta_1 = -\theta_2 = \pi/3$, $\phi_1 = \pi/2$, and $\phi_2 = \pi/2$, $\hbar\omega = 1.5 \gamma_0$ and $\zeta = 0.1$.

order to do so, we calculated the LDOS around the polarization interfaces of the laser pattern and weighted them according to the different Floquet replicas. A similar procedure can be done for the transmission amplitudes of Eq. (S19).

In columns (A) and (B) of Fig. S5 we show the LDOS evaluated at the interface regions generated by the laser configuration of Eq. (3). Column (A) corresponds to the interface with linear polarization along y , while column (B) shows the LDOS at the interface with linear polarization along x , see Fig. 3. In rows (a) and (b) we use an armchair ribbon (AGNR), while in (c) and (d) we use a zigzag ribbon (ZGNR). In addition, in rows (b) and (d), columns (A) and (B), we show a normalized difference between the weighted LDOS in replicas $n = 0$ and 1, according to:

$$\delta_{i,k}(\epsilon) = \tanh\left(\frac{\Delta\rho_{i,k}(\epsilon)}{\xi}\right), \quad (\text{S21})$$

with $\xi = 5$ a constant introduced to reduce contrast in the density difference, $\Delta\rho_{i,k} = \rho_{i,k}^{(0)} - \rho_{i,k}^{(1)}$, and

$$\rho_{i,k}^{(n)}(\epsilon) = -\frac{1}{\pi} \lim_{\eta \rightarrow 0^+} \text{Im}\{[\mathbf{G}_k(\epsilon + i\eta)]_{i,i}^{n,n}\}, \quad (\text{S22})$$

the LDOS weighted on the n replica. Finally, column (C) shows the time-averaged transmission imbalance $\delta\mathcal{T}^{(0)}$ in (a) and (c), while in (b) and (d) we decompose the transmission amplitudes with respect to its direction of propagation [\mathcal{T}_{RL} (green) and \mathcal{T}_{LR} (orange)] and its weight on the $n = 0$ (solid) and 1 (dotted) Floquet replica.

A finite replica difference in the LDOS indicates that the associated Floquet-Bloch state $|\epsilon_k\rangle$ has different weights in the considered Floquet replicas, i.e., $|\epsilon_k\rangle = c_0 |\epsilon_k, 0\rangle + c_1 |\epsilon_k, 1\rangle$, with $|c_0| \neq |c_1|$. This is particularly clear for the FIS in almost all cases. Let us take for example the AGNR case. Here we can see in (A,b) that the FIS propagate from right to left and their weights change sign around $\hbar\omega/2$. For (B,b), on the other hand, the FIS propagate from left to right, and they have almost opposite weights along the whole gap region.

An intuitive connection between these LDOS differences $\Delta\rho_{i,k}$ and the transmission amplitudes can be established by performing a k -integral on the Brillouin zone, such that for (A,b) this yields a finite imbalance between the replicas, while for (B,b) this integral is almost balanced. This behavior has a strong impact on the transmission amplitudes shown in panel (C,b), where a clear energy dependence appears for the $\text{R} \rightarrow \text{L}$ channels. In contrast, the $\text{L} \rightarrow \text{R}$ channels are almost energy independent within the gap. In addition, when summing up the two replica contributions for a given channel, e.g., $\mathcal{T}_{\text{RL}}^{(0)} +$

$\mathcal{T}_{\text{RL}}^{(1)}$, one recovers almost quantized transmission,^{7,8} whose value counts the number of Floquet interface and edge states propagating in the evaluated direction. As this value is the same for the two interfaces, the weight difference of the two $n = 0$ channels yields the transmission imbalance shown in (C,a).

A similar analysis can be applied to the ZGNR, where again clear imbalance appears between the different replica contributions to both the LDOS and the transmission amplitudes. We can see in panel (C,c) that for $\epsilon \sim \hbar\omega/2$ the time-averaged transmission imbalance presents opposite signs as compared with the AGNR case of panel (C,a), meaning that such a quantity indeed depends on the edge geometry of the sample.

Role of disorder.— Another interesting point to address is the effect of disorder on the obtained photocurrents. Although a detailed calculation of the transmission amplitudes including, e.g., random vacancies through the sample is beyond the scope of this work, the presence of Floquet topological states, either located at the physical boundaries or the polarization interfaces, is robust against this type of perturbation.⁹ On the other hand, the presence of random vacancies in the ribbon naturally breaks inversion symmetry, thus contributing to the generation of zero-bias photocurrents.¹⁰ Therefore, we expect a competition between the above effect introduced by the laser ($\bar{\mathcal{I}}_{\text{laser}}$) and that given by disorder ($\bar{\mathcal{I}}_{\text{dis}}$). For example, in Ref. [10] a disorder contribution of $\bar{\mathcal{I}}_{\text{dis}} \sim 5 \mu\text{A}$ was obtained for $\sim 0.1\%$ vacancy density in illuminated graphene for a two-terminal transport setup. This means that the contribution per channel would be of $\bar{\mathcal{I}}_{\text{dis}}/4 \sim 1.25 \mu\text{A}$. In our setup, on the other hand, the laser contribution per channel [Fig. 4(a) inset] is $\bar{\mathcal{I}}_{\text{laser}}/16 \sim 10 \mu\text{A}$. Adding up to this difference, while the direction of $\bar{\mathcal{I}}_{\text{laser}}$ is fixed through the change in the polarization handedness across the interface or physical edge, the direction of $\bar{\mathcal{I}}_{\text{dis}}$ may depend on the specific disorder arrangement within the interface region. In this sense, we expect no strong modifications to the photocurrents of Fig. 4 as far as the FIS are preserved.¹¹ Our hypothesis rests on the fact that, by increasing the number of interfaces, the disorder contribution to the photocurrent $\bar{\mathcal{I}}_{\text{dis}}$ should average out since it does not have a preferential direction in each supercell, while the $\bar{\mathcal{I}}_{\text{laser}}$ contribution is always the same and therefore it grows with the number of interfaces. As an experimental proposal, by varying λ or θ , the number of supercells n_{sc} could be increased, so that in a given disordered sample the expected photocurrent grows as $(4n_{\text{sc}} + 1)/5$, while deviations from this value due to $\bar{\mathcal{I}}_{\text{dis}}$ should decrease. In any case, this intriguing topic would deserve further exploration.

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¹ For graphene, we can use $\epsilon_i = 0$ for all sites.

² J. H. Shirley, "Solution of the Schrödinger Equation with a Hamiltonian Periodic in Time," *Phys. Rev.* **138**, B979 (1965).

³ H. Samba, "Steady states and quasienergies of a quantum-mechanical system in an oscillating field," *Phys. Rev. A* **7**, 2203

(1973).

⁴ S. Kohler, J. Lehmann, and P. Hänggi, "Driven quantum transport on the nanoscale," *Phys. Rep.* **406**, 379 (2005).

⁵ H. L. Calvo, P. M. Perez-Piskunow, H. M. Pastawski, S. Roche, and L. E. F. Foa Torres, "Non-perturbative effects of laser illumination on the electrical properties of graphene nanoribbons," *J.*

Figure S5. Replica weighted LDOS and transmission coefficients. Columns (A) and (B) show the LDOS at interfaces linearly polarized along y and x , respectively, according to Fig. 3. For these columns, rows (b) and (d) correspond to the LDOS difference of Eq. (S21), for AGNR ($\tilde{a} = 3a$) and ZGNR ($\tilde{a} = \sqrt{3}a$), respectively. Column (C) shows transmission amplitudes: (a) and (c) show the corresponding time-averaged transmission imbalance, while (b) and (d) are the transmission coefficients for the different replicas and transport direction. Green (orange) denote $L \rightarrow R$ ($R \rightarrow L$) propagation, while solid and dotted lines denote the 0-th and 1-th replica contribution, respectively. We used $\zeta_1 = \zeta_2 = 0.2$ and $\hbar\omega = 1.5\gamma_0$. For the AGNR LDOS we used $N = 1400$ unit cells and for the ZGNR LDOS we used $N = 800$. For the calculation of the transmission coefficients, we used a single supercell composed by $N = 200$ unit cells.

Phys.: *Condens. Matter* **25**, 144202 (2013).

⁶ H. L. Calvo, L. E. F. Foa Torres, P. M. Perez-Piskunow, C. A. Balseiro, and G. Usaj, “Floquet interface states in illuminated three-dimensional topological insulators,” *Phys. Rev. B* **91**, 241404(R) (2015).

⁷ A. Kundu and B. Seradjeh, “Transport signatures of floquet majorana fermions in driven topological superconductors,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **111**, 136402 (2013).

⁸ A. Farrell and T. Pereg-Barnea, “Edge-state transport in floquet topological insulators,” *Phys. Rev. B* **93**, 045121 (2016).

⁹ P. M. Perez-Piskunow, G. Usaj, C. A. Balseiro, and L. E. F. Foa Torres, “Floquet chiral edge states in graphene,” *Phys. Rev. B* **89**, 121401 (2014).

¹⁰ L. E. F. Foa Torres, P. M. Perez-Piskunow, C. A. Balseiro, and G. Usaj, “Multiterminal Conductance of a Floquet Topological Insulator,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **113**, 266801 (2014).

¹¹ This implies that the localization length of the FIS should remain smaller than the separation between adjacent interfaces.